

Uniform, Invertible Lambert W-Based Approximations for Fermi-Dirac Integrals in the Degenerate and Crossover Regimes

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2026-03-14

Abstract

We present preliminary results for a family of smooth, invertible and uniform approximations of the Fermi-Dirac integrals $f_{1/2}$, $f_{3/2}$ and $f_{5/2}$ in the degenerate and crossover regimes using Lambert W functions with two fixed parameters, which are tunable for different fugacity ranges. The maximal relative errors throughout the eight orders of magnitude of the primary fugacity range $10^2 < z < 10^{10}$ are less than 1.6% for all three integrals, with further lower worst-case errors attained for a crossover range $10 < z < 10^2$ (less than 0.4%) and a higher fugacity range $10^6 < z < 10^{18}$ (less than 0.9%). The Lambert W structure enables analytical inversion, yielding closed-form expressions for the chemical potential $\mu(n, T)$ without numerical iteration.

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1 Introduction

This text presents preliminary results for a family of smooth, invertible, and uniform approximants of the Fermi-Dirac integrals $f_{1/2}$, $f_{3/2}$ and $f_{5/2}$ using Lambert W forms with two tunable constant parameters, with relatively low maximal relative errors across wide fugacity ranges. A more comprehensive article is under preparation.

This preliminary report includes the Lambert W approximations themselves, and the optimal parameters that have been found so far for the three different fugacity ranges. The mathematical framework, connecting the Fermi-Dirac integrals with polylogarithms and their series definitions, is described in section 2. The derived forms of the three Lambert W expressions, one for each Fermi-Dirac integral, are presented in section 3. In this section the relative error metric is defined and the numerical method for determining the optimal values of the two parameters are also described.

Speculative applications and possible favorable properties of the approximants are discussed in section 4. Error plots and tables, including the thus far optimal parameters to high precision, are presented in section 5. Section A of the appendix describes the derivation of the approximant of order $s = 3/2$. Section B uses the Lambert W inversion property to derive a closed-form, but approximate, expression for $\mu(n, T)$. Section C gives a detailed description of the relevant properties of the Lambert W function.

2 Definitions

In this text, references will be made to both Fermi-Dirac integrals $f_s(z)$, polylogarithms $-\text{Li}_s(-z)$ and their corresponding Lambert W approximations $L_s(z)$. They are defined so that the half-integer order s of each function is in agreement with its two counterparts.

2.1 Fermi-Dirac integrals

The notation and definitions used (cf. for example Huang [1, 187-188]), for the Fermi-Dirac integrals is

$$f_{1/2}(z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1/2)} \int_0^\infty \frac{t^{-1/2}}{z^{-1}e^t + 1} dt, \quad (2.1)$$

$$f_{3/2}(z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} \int_0^\infty \frac{t^{1/2}}{z^{-1}e^t + 1} dt \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$f_{5/2}(z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(5/2)} \int_0^\infty \frac{t^{3/2}}{z^{-1}e^t + 1} dt, \quad (2.3)$$

where $z = \exp(\mu/k_B T)$ is the fugacity and $\Gamma(x)$ the gamma function.

2.2 Polylogarithms

The corresponding polylogarithms, for complex ζ , are defined [2, 27, 1.11]

$$-\text{Li}_{1/2}(-\zeta) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-\zeta)^k}{k^{1/2}}, \quad (2.4)$$

$$-\text{Li}_{3/2}(-\zeta) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-\zeta)^k}{k^{3/2}}, \quad (2.5)$$

and

$$-\text{Li}_{5/2}(-\zeta) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-\zeta)^k}{k^{5/2}}. \quad (2.6)$$

These series converge only for $|\zeta| < 1$. While it may be considered a known result, in the full paper it will be shown using the interior uniqueness theorem (cf. [3, 369-370]) and Weierstrass' theorem on uniformly convergent sequences of analytic functions (cf. [3, 330]), that the Fermi-Dirac integrals of a particular order $s = 1/2, 3/2, 5/2$, coincide in value with the corresponding series definitions for all complex ζ with $\text{Re } \zeta > 0$, and in particular all real numbers $z > 0$, and also that the integral representation is analytic for all

$\text{Re } \zeta > 0$. From this follows that the Fermi-Dirac integrals can be considered the analytic continuation of the polylogarithms, as initially defined by their series for $0 < z < 1$, to all fugacity values $z > 0$.

3 Lambert W expressions

The principal branch of the Lambert W function is denoted $W_0(x)$. The family of Lambert W approximations are

$$L_{1/2}(z) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Az^B)]^{1/2}, \quad (3.1)$$

$$L_{3/2}(z) = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Az^B)]^{3/2}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$L_{5/2}(z) = \frac{8}{15\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Az^B)]^{5/2}. \quad (3.3)$$

Here, A and B are positive constants which are fixed. They are designed to interpolate between the small- z corresponding to the Boltzmann approximation. Their leading coefficients are chosen to match those of the Sommerfeld expansions of the corresponding Fermi-Dirac integrals. The exponents are likewise derived by the order required to match the large z asymptotic form given by the Sommerfeld expansions evaluated in $\ln z$.

The derivation of $L_{3/2}(z)$ is described in section A in the appendix.

3.1 Error analysis

The relative error of the approximation $L_{3/2}(z)$ is given by

$$\delta(z) = \frac{\left| \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Az^B)]^{3/2} - [-\text{Li}_{3/2}(-z)] \right|}{|-\text{Li}_{3/2}(-z)|}, \quad (3.4)$$

and equivalently for the two other orders $s = 1/2$ and $s = 5/2$. The values of these errors for large numbers (thousands) of logarithmically spaced fugacities z were computed in Python using the NumPy, SciPy and MPMath packages.

3.2 Determination of parameters A and B

The two parameters A and B are fixed and positive real numbers. They are determined for a given fugacity range I , i.e. $z_{\min} < z < z_{\max}$ by an algorithm that tests various combinations of A and B values in a grid pattern, converging on the combination which minimizes the maximum relative error $\max_{z \in I} \delta(z)$ encountered on a specified fugacity interval. The main program is implemented in Fortran, but computation of Fermi-Dirac integrals and of Lambert W expressions are handled by their reference implementations in GSL¹ via C bindings.

Three fugacity intervals have so far been evaluated, with optimal parameters and error bounds established for the Lambert W approximations for each of the Fermi-Dirac integrals $f_{1/2}(z)$, $f_{3/2}(z)$ and $f_{5/2}(z)$.

- *Primary range*: $10^2 < z < 10^{10}$
- *Crossover range*: $10 < z < 10^2$
- *Astrophysical range*: $10^6 < z < 10^{18}$

4 Properties of the Lambert W forms

Here, possibly useful properties of the approximants are discussed. The list is speculative and in a very early stage of development.

¹GNU Scientific Library; the version of the library used is 2.8.

4.1 Smoothness

The Lambert W function is infinitely differentiable. This allows the analytical derivation of properties such as specific heat C_V , susceptibility χ and compressibility κ , and makes the error in evaluating these expressions predictable by standard methods for estimating error propagation, as the relative error of the parent approximation is known for each point z in the fugacity range. Combined with the uniformity of the expression (that is, the approximations are not piece-wise defined and hence not only piece-wise smooth), there are no discontinuities introduced.

A possible immediate consequence is that simulations on fermionic systems which require repeated computation of derivatives might receive significant speed-ups given the analytic properties and the avoidance of computationally intensive numerical steps such as root-finding. In addition, when thermodynamical quantities are computed by differentiation, the known error bounds for any fugacity z may improve numerical stability, in particular when higher order derivatives are needed (see also section 4.3 for a discussion on implications to numerical methods).

4.2 Analytical invertibility

Potentially useful is also the invertibility of the Lambert W expressions. For example, from the relation [4, 247, Eq. 4]²

$$\frac{1}{2}n\lambda_T^3 = f_{3/2}(z), \quad (4.1)$$

this invertibility enables the direct, explicit expression of the fugacity $\mu(n, T)$ in terms of the number density n and the temperature T , with the error in evaluation bounded by the accuracy of the approximation in the particular fugacity range considered. Here λ_T is the thermal wavelength [5, 17]

$$\lambda_T \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi\hbar^2}{mk_B T}}, \quad (4.2)$$

where m is the mass of each particle and k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

The inverse of the relation in Eq. (4.1) is then given by

$$\mu(n, T) \approx \frac{k_B T}{B} \left[\frac{2}{3} \ln \left(\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{8} n \lambda_T^3 \right) + \left(\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{8} n \lambda_T^3 \right)^{2/3} - \ln A \right], \quad (4.3)$$

where A and B are the constants of the approximation. This result is derived in section B in the appendix.

4.3 Tunability and known error bounds

For each combination of the two parameters A and B , the relative error can be easily computed. As is shown in the plots, the magnitudes of error outside the optimized range can be characterized and are in some cases favorable. For simulations that involve iterations that require repeated root finding, the approximations (and the evaluations of their derived quantities) could deliver estimates from approximate thermodynamical relations that are unchanging in form (for example, the partial derivative $\partial\mu/\partial n$, which could be derived analytically from Eq. (B.10) always has the same expression) with bounded errors. The implementation of the described approximants into numerical solvers could possibly improve numerical stability and accelerate convergence to a specified tolerance by allowing some iterations of the numerical algorithm to be skipped.

4.4 Uniformity

Each approximation, while its precision decays outside its optimized interval, has the same form for all $z > 0$. In addition, the three functions $L_s(z)$ (i.e. for a given order $s = 1/2, 3/2, 5/2$) are identical in form except for varying constants A and B and the initial constant coefficient. There are in some cases large regions of overlap with low error between families of approximations, and it is likely that with more sophisticated

²The factor $1/2$ accounts for the spin degeneracy $g = 2S + 1$ of the (fermionic) particle; of most immediate interest is the electron with $S = 1/2$.

statistical methods (minimal worst case error might not be the best metric for all cases) and algorithms useful fugacity ranges other than the three shown here will be found.

This could allow for stitching together differently optimized approximants of the same order (for example the $L_{5/2}(z)$ approximant for the crossover regime with its counterpart optimized for the astrophysical range; see Figs. 3 and 9) in a way that would still avoid discontinuities. It is however not clear that this would be compatible with the derivation of thermodynamical quantities and relations by differentiation without introducing discontinuities (i.e., if smoothness, or at least differentiability some desired minimal order, could be maintained), and the utility of this approach needs further investigation.

4.5 Approximate thermodynamic consistency

The availability of approximations for all three Fermi-Dirac integrals $f_{1/2}$, $f_{3/2}$ and $f_{5/2}$ may unlock a full description of thermodynamical quantities that is approximately thermodynamically consistent across the wide fugacity ranges of the examined intervals (in particular the primary interval, spanning eight orders of magnitude, and the astrophysical interval, spanning 12 orders of magnitude). While a derivation is not included here, for example the grand potential Ω may be derived by inversion of from the integral $f_{5/2}(z)$ in analogy with Eq. (B.10).

In this manner, a full set of thermodynamical quantities could be derived from a functional form that is consistently defined, aside from different constants between approximants of different order s , and varying error across the fugacity ranges. This may result in the maintenance of consistency in the relations between thermodynamical quantities derived from the approximations, in a warped but continuous structure that is not broken by discontinuities introduced by piece-wise definitions, reflecting the smoothness and relatively slowly varying error across large fugacity ranges.

5 Error plots

Here, error plots are provided for the different approximants and the three fugacity ranges, with the relative error defined by Eq. 3.4, and the errors evaluated by the methodology (calculation in Python using NumPy, SciPy and MPMath) described in subsection 3.2. The graphs are constructed by evaluating the error in 6000 logarithmically spaced z points.

In addition, for ease of reproduction of the graphs, the computed parameters and their associated maximal errors, for each approximant in each targeted fugacity range, are provided to high precision in tables at the end of each subsection.

5.1 Primary range ($10^2 < z < 10^{10}$)

The relative error of $L_{1/2}(z)$ over the primary range is shown in Fig. 1. Here it is especially noteworthy that the error rapidly increases for fugacities lower than $z = 10^2$, but rises much more slowly for higher fugacities. The maximal error is 0.994%, and approximately in the range $3 \times 10^5 < z < 2 \times 10^8$ the error is lower than 0.5%.

For $L_{3/2}(z)$, the relative error over the primary range is shown in Fig. 2. Like for $L_{1/2}(z)$ the error rapidly increases for fugacities lower than $z = 10^2$, but rises more slowly, but faster than for $L_{1/2}(z)$ for higher fugacities. The maximal error is 1.540%, and approximately in the range $3 \times 10^6 < z < 2 \times 10^8$ the error is lower than 0.5%.

For $L_{5/2}(z)$, the relative error over the primary range is shown in Fig. 3. Here it is especially noteworthy that the error rapidly increases for fugacities lower than $z = 10^2$, but rises much more slowly for higher fugacities. The maximal error is 1.337%, and approximately in the range $3 \times 10^6 < z < 2 \times 10^8$ the error is lower than 0.5%.

Precise values for the parameters A and B and the maximal errors are given in table 1.

Table 1: High-precision parameters for the primary range $10^2 < z < 10^{10}$

	A	B	Maximal error
$L_{1/2}(z)$	2.2704676169042259381570	1.1197598799399699487367	0.994365496%
$L_{3/2}(z)$	4.0957286432160806555203	1.0873115577889447269655	1.540947695%
$L_{5/2}(z)$	6.3011555777888945684140	1.0666966966966966445796	1.336774887%

Figure 1: **Primary range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z \approx 0$ to $z = 10^{13}$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{1/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 4.09572\dots$ and $B = 1.08731\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the primary fugacity interval $10^2 < z < 10^{10}$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 0.994%.

5.2 Crossover range ($10 < z < 10^2$)

The maximal errors within the crossover range are 0.3961% for $L_{1/2}(z)$, 0.1364% for $L_{3/2}(z)$ and 0.2368% for $L_{5/2}(z)$ (see Figs. 4, 5 and 3 respectively). Precise values for the parameters A and B and the maximal errors are given in table 2.

Note that due to the large differences in the shapes of the error curves, the displayed fugacity ranges vary between the plots. The ranges of the vertical axes showing relative errors also vary.

Particularly noteworthy is the behavior of $L_{5/2}(z)$: While its error rises to about 0.8% somewhat about $z = 10^3$, the error then falls again, reaching zero at a point between $z = 10^4$ and $z = 10^6$, before beginning to rise again.

Table 2: High-precision parameters for the crossover range $10 < z < 10^2$

	A	B	Maximal error
$L_{1/2}(z)$	0.5857947434292866129013	1.3998797595190379805530	0.396117747%
$L_{3/2}(z)$	2.5937421777221527641188	1.1747494989979958557313	0.136383408%
$L_{5/2}(z)$	5.6887443721860924128464	1.0806206206206205866494	0.236720544%

Figure 2: **Primary range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z \approx 0$ to $z = 10^{13}$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{3/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 4.09572\dots$ and $B = 1.08731\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the primary fugacity interval $10^2 < z < 10^{10}$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 1.540 %.

Figure 3: **Primary range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z \approx 0$ to $z = 10^{13}$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{5/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 6.30256\dots$ and $B = 1.06669\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the primary fugacity interval $10^2 < z < 10^{10}$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 1.336 %. The relative error is displayed along the vertical axis from 0% to 1 %.

Figure 4: **Crossover range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z = 1$ to $z = 500$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{1/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 9.3178\dots$ and $B = 1.0410\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the crossover fugacity interval $10 < z < 10^2$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 0.396%. The relative error is displayed along the vertical axis from 0% to 2%.

Figure 5: **Crossover range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z = 1$ to $z = 800$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{3/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 9.3178\dots$ and $B = 1.0410\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the crossover fugacity interval $10 < z < 10^2$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 0.136%. The relative error is displayed along the vertical axis from 0% to 1%.

Figure 6: **Crossover range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z = 1$ to $z = 10^9$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{5/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 5.6887\dots$ and $B = 1.0806\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the crossover fugacity interval $10 < z < 10^2$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 0.237%. The relative error is displayed along the vertical axis from 0% to 3%.

5.3 Astrophysical range ($10^6 < z < 10^{18}$)

The maximal errors within the astrophysical range are 0.2000 % for $L_{1/2}(z)$, 0.4081 % for $L_{3/2}(z)$ and 0.8611 % for $L_{5/2}(z)$ (see Figs. 7, 8 and 9 respectively). Precise values for the parameters A and B and the maximal errors are given in table 3.

Note that the vertical scale in the plots is different from the primary range plots: It here ranges from 0% to 2%. Note also that due to numerical issues in the Python implementation involving NumPy, SciPy and MPMath, the horizontal scale could not be extended to fugacities higher than $z = 10^{19}$.

Table 3: High-precision parameters for the astrophysical range $10^6 < z < 10^{18}$

	A	B	Maximal error
$L_{1/2}(z)$	7.7000000000000001776357	1.0418546365914786999696	0.199956524 %
$L_{3/2}(z)$	8.9942428035043793244085	1.0390977443609024089000	0.480729672 %
$L_{5/2}(z)$	9.3177096370463079466617	1.0410025062656642624859	0.861143508 %

Figure 7: **Astrophysical range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z = 10^4$ to $z = 10^{19}$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{1/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 7.70000\dots$ and $B = 1.0419\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the primary fugacity interval $10^6 < z < 10^{18}$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 0.200 %. The relative error is displayed along the vertical axis from 0% to 2%.

Figure 8: **Astrophysical range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z = 10^4$ to $z = 10^{19}$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{3/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 8.9942\dots$ and $B = 1.0391\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the primary fugacity interval $10^6 < z < 10^{18}$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 0.481%. The relative error is displayed along the vertical axis from 0% to 2%.

Figure 9: **Astrophysical range:** Semilogarithmic plot, from $z = 10^4$ to $z = 10^{19}$, of the relative error $\delta(z)$ of the $L_{5/2}(z)$ approximation with parameters $A = 9.3178\dots$ and $B = 1.0410\dots$, when the approximation is optimized for the primary fugacity interval $10^6 < z < 10^{18}$. Within this interval, bounded by vertical lines, the maximal error is 0.861%. The relative error is displayed along the vertical axis from 0% to 2%.

A Derivation of the Lambert W approximant $L_{3/2}(z)$

A.1 Construction of the approximation

For small values of the fugacity z , that is $z \ll 1$, the approximation

$$f_{3/2}(z) = -\text{Li}_{3/2}(-z) = -\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-z)^k}{k^{3/2}} = z - \frac{z^2}{2^{3/2}} + \dots \approx z \quad (\text{A.1})$$

is assumed to hold. We will further define $z \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e^w \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e^{\mu/k_B T}$. For large values of z , an asymptotic series is derived using the Sommerfeld expansion in section D of the appendix:

$$f_{3/2}(z) = f_{3/2}(e^w) = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} w^{3/2} \left[1 + \frac{\pi^2}{8} w^{-2} + \frac{7\pi^4}{640} w^{-4} + \dots \right], \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Here it is noteworthy that the bracketed part of the expression tends toward unity as $z = e^w \rightarrow \infty$. Hence, up to leading order, $f_{3/2}(e^w) \sim w^{3/2}$ for large values of $w = \ln z$.

The Maclaurin series for the Lambert W function is [6, 339]

$$W_0(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-k)^{k-1}}{k!} x^k, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

so that for $x \ll 1$, $W_0(x) \approx x$. An asymptotic expansion of $W_0(x)$ for large x is given by Eq. (C.5) in the appendix:

$$W_0(x) \sim \ln x - \ln \ln x + \dots \quad (\text{A.4})$$

As it is known that the fugacity z , through the relationship $z = e^w = e^{\mu/k_B T}$, can only attain real, positive values, only the principal branch $W_0(x)$ of the Lambert W function needs to be considered [6, 330-331].

Any ansatz containing the principal branch $W_0(x)$ of the Lambert W function must reproduce the correct order of at least the leading term of the asymptotic expansion of $f_{3/2}(z)$ in Eq. (A.2), in order for the approximation not to diverge from it for large values of z :

$$[W_0(x)]^{3/2} \sim (\ln x)^{3/2} \left[1 - \frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x} + \frac{\ln \ln x}{(\ln x)^2} + \dots \right]^{3/2}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Care must be taken here: Erdélyi [7, 11-12] distinguishes between asymptotic *expansions*, which may be divergent or convergent, and *asymptotic series*. However, Corless et al. show that the asymptotic relation in Eq. C.5 (as a special case of Eqs. (4.19) and (4.20) in [6, 349-350]) is an asymptotic series. Despite the property of convergence (i.e. there is not a particular number of terms beyond which the error begins to increase for sufficiently large values of x), only a few terms will be needed for the asymptotic matching with the expression derived from the Sommerfeld expansion. Truncation after the second term and expanding the bracketed expression around $x = 0$ to the first order gives

$$[W_0(x)]^{3/2} \approx (\ln x)^{3/2} \left[1 - \frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x} \right]^{3/2} \approx (\ln x)^{3/2} \left[1 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x} \right]. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Here the two terms in the bracketed expression were combined as

$$1 - \frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x} = 1 - \delta \quad (\text{A.7})$$

and the Maclaurin expansion

$$(1 - \delta)^{3/2} = 1 - \frac{3}{2} \delta + \mathcal{O}(\delta^2), \quad (\text{A.8})$$

valid for $|\delta| < 1$, was used. With the substitution $t = \ln x$ and $t \rightarrow \infty$ when $x \rightarrow \infty$, a standard limit gives $\ln \ln x / \ln x = \ln t / t \rightarrow 0$ when $t \rightarrow \infty$. Hence above any sufficiently large value of x , the magnitude of the term $\delta = \ln \ln x / \ln x$ will be smaller than any given constant, in particular it will be smaller than 1.

The most general Lambert W form ansatz that interpolates between the small z behavior $f_{3/2}(z) \approx z = e^w$ and the large w behavior $f_{3/2}(z) \approx \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} w^{3/2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} (\ln z)^{3/2}$ is given by

$$\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Ae^{Bw})]^{3/2}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where A and B are parameters to be fixed. This ansatz will be justified, and the parameters A and B assigned appropriate (intermediate³) values, in the following subsection.

A.2 Reproduction of asymptotics and fitting of parameters

A.2.1 Relation for determining $f_{3/2}(1)$

A useful relation provided⁴ in [8, 160, § 58, footnote 2] is the integral

$$I(x) = \int_0^\infty \frac{t^{x-1}}{e^t + 1} dt = (1 - 2^{1-x})\Gamma(x)\zeta(x) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

expressed on the right in terms of the gamma function and the Riemann zeta function. Comparison with the definition of $f_{3/2}(z)$, on integral form, in Eq. (D.1) in the appendix, shows that

$$f_{3/2}(1) = \frac{I(3/2)}{\Gamma(3/2)} = (1 - 2^{-1/2})\zeta(3/2). \quad (\text{A.11})$$

A.2.2 Asymptotic behavior for $z \rightarrow 0^+$

For small $w = \ln z$, the Maclaurin expansion gives

$$\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Ae^{Bw})]^{3/2} \approx \frac{4A}{3\sqrt{\pi}} e^{(3/2)Bw} \sim e^{(3/2)Bw} = z^{(3/2)B}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where it was used that $w \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \ln z$. Using equation A.11 that gives an exact value for $f_{3/2}(1)$, the value of A can now be fixed: Since $z = e^w = 1$, $e^{Bw} = (e^w)^B = 1$, and therefore

$$\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Ae^{Bw})]^{3/2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(A)]^{3/2} = (1 - 1/\sqrt{2})\zeta(3/2) \quad (\text{A.13})$$

for $z = 1$. This result can be rewritten

$$W_0(A) = \left[\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{4} (1 - 1/\sqrt{2}) \zeta(3/2) \right]^{2/3}, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

from which it follows, by the inversion relationship in Eq. (C.2), that

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \left[\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{4} (1 - 1/\sqrt{2}) \zeta(3/2) \right]^{2/3} \exp \left(\left[\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{4} (1 - 1/\sqrt{2}) \zeta(3/2) \right]^{2/3} \right) \\ &= 2.780762655 \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

A.2.3 Asymptotic behavior for $z \rightarrow +\infty$

Using the asymptotic expression for $W_0(x)$ derived in Eq. (A.6), the ansatz has, to leading order, the asymptotic form

$$\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Ae^{Bw})]^{3/2} \sim \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [\ln(Ae^{Bw})]^{3/2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [\ln A + Bw]^{3/2}, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

for large z . This can be rewritten as

$$\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [\ln A + Bw]^{3/2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} \left[Bw \left(1 + \frac{\ln A}{B} w^{-1} \right) \right]^{3/2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} (Bw)^{3/2} \left(1 + \frac{\ln A}{B} w^{-1} \right)^{3/2}. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

Setting $[(\ln A)/B] w^{-1} = -\delta$, the Maclaurin expansion in Eq. (A.8) can be used to expand the last factor as

³That is to say, the derivation proceeds with analytically derived values for A and B , which however must be optimized numerically to provide more accurate approximations.

⁴Note that a German translation of Landau-Lifshitz has been used. Here and wherever it is cited, the section number is provided in addition to the page numbers to help readers with the book in other languages.

$$\left(1 + \frac{\ln A}{B} w^{-1}\right)^{3/2} = 1 + \frac{3}{2} \frac{\ln A}{B} w^{-1} + \mathcal{O}\left(\left[\frac{\ln A}{B}\right]^2 w^{-2}\right), \quad (\text{A.18})$$

with convergence for $|\delta| = \left| \left[\frac{\ln A}{B}\right] w^{-1} \right| < 1$. As $\ln A$ and B are constants, this is fulfilled for any $w = \ln z$ sufficiently large. The expanded factor tends to unity as w tends to infinity. The result is that for large $w = \ln z$ and to leading order,

$$\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Ae^{Bw})]^{3/2} \sim \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} (Bw)^{3/2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} (B \ln z)^{3/2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [\ln(z^B)]^{3/2}. \quad (\text{A.19})$$

This is now compared to the approximation of the Fermi-Dirac integral, valid for large z , which was derived using the Sommerfeld expansion (cf. section D in the appendix). By Eq. (D.14), it can be written in $\ln z$ as

$$f_{3/2}(\ln z) = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} (\ln z)^{3/2} \left[1 + \frac{\pi^2}{8} (\ln z)^{-2} + \frac{7\pi^4}{640} (\ln z)^{-4} \dots \right], \quad (\text{A.20})$$

whose leading order term is $\left[\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} \right] (\ln z)^{3/2}$.

To leading order in $w = \ln z$, the large z asymptotic for the Lambert W ansatz, as expressed in Eqs. (A.16) and (A.19), must match with the Sommerfeld approximation, in order for the approximations not to diverge from each other as z increases. Comparing Eqs. (D.14) and (A.19) provides the condition that $B = 1$, fixing this second and final parameter.

A.3 Intermediate form of the Lambert W approximation and analysis

With $A = 2.780762655\dots$ and $B = 1$ fixed, and noting that $e^{Bw} = e^{B \ln z} = z$, the ansatz in Eq. (A.9) now has the form

$$L_{3/2}(z) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Az)]^{3/2} \approx \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(2.7808z)]^{3/2}. \quad (\text{A.21})$$

For illustrative purposes, the approximation with these intermediate parameters is shown in Fig. 10. It should be noted that with $B = 1$, a comparison between the Maclaurin expansion of the ansatz for the Lambert W approximation (see Eq. (A.12) and the expansion for $f_{3/2}(z) \approx z$ (for $z \ll 1$) in Eq. (A.1) shows that with $B = 1$, they now diverge: To leading order, the Lambert W approximation is now asymptotically $z^{3/2}$ for $z \ll 1$, as seen in Eq. (A.12). This will inevitably and adversely affect the accuracy of the Lambert W approximation for small z .

As the parameter B was set to unity to match the asymptotic behaviors of the approximations for large values of z , this points to a conflict between accuracy in the low and high ranges. The parameter A could also have been chosen differently: It was fixed using the exact value of the Fermi-Dirac integral at $z = 1$ because a convenient relation, that in Eq. (A.10) was available. However, $W_0(Az_0)$, with z_0 a particular fixed value of z , and from there A by inversion of the Lambert W function, could be computed (if not else numerically) for any value of z , and the point where the approximation is chosen to be exact placed at any $z > 0$. This is precisely what leads to the parameter scan described in section 3.2.

B Derivation of the inversion relationship for the chemical potential $\mu(n, T)$

Proceeding from the exact relation (cf. Eq. (4.1))

$$\frac{1}{2} n \lambda_T^3 = f_{3/2}(z), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

and replacing the Fermi-Dirac integral with its approximation,

$$\frac{1}{2} n \lambda_T^3 \approx L_{3/2}(z) = \frac{4}{\sqrt{3\pi}} [W_0(Az^B)]^{3/2}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

moving constants and exponentiating both sides by $2/3$ yields

$$\left(\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{8} n \lambda_T^3 \right)^{2/3} = W_0(Az^B). \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Now defining

Figure 10: The relative error $\delta(z)$ of the Lambert W approximation $\frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(Az)]^{3/2} \approx \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} [W_0(2.7808z)]^{3/2}$ of the Fermi-Dirac integral $f_{3/2}(z)$. Note the exploding error as the value of z decreases into the classical regime, due to the mismatch in orders for small z , and the slow convergence to the Sommerfeld expansion for very large values of z as the terms within brackets in Eqs. (A.19) and (A.9) converge to unity. See also section A.3 in the text.

$$u \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{8} n \lambda_T^3, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

the equation becomes

$$W_0(Az^B) = u^{2/3} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

As $u(n, T)$ and Az^B , given that $A, B > 0$, both can take on only strictly positive values, the inversion relationship in Eq. (C.2) for the principal branch of the Lambert W function is applicable:

$$W_0(x) = w \Leftrightarrow x = we^w. \quad (\text{B.6})$$

From this follows that

$$Az^B = u^{2/3} \exp(u^{2/3}). \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Taking the logarithms of both sides yields

$$\ln A + B \ln z = \frac{2}{3} \ln u + u^{2/3}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

which may be rearranged to

$$\ln z = \frac{1}{B} \left[\frac{2}{3} \ln u + u^{2/3} - \ln A \right]. \quad (\text{B.9})$$

With $\ln z = \mu/k_B T$, and reintroducing n and λ_T in place of u , one arrives at the final expression

$$\mu(n, T) = \frac{k_B T}{B} \left[\frac{2}{3} \ln \left(\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{8} n \lambda_T^3 \right) + \left(\frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{8} n \lambda_T^3 \right)^{2/3} - \ln A \right], \quad (\text{B.10})$$

where μ is the chemical potential, n the volumetric number density of particles, T the temperature, λ_T the thermal wavelength, and A and B finally the constants appearing in $L_{3/2}(z)$ (see Eq. (3.2)).

C Properties of the Lambert W function

C.1 Real-valued branches

Figure 11: Various values of the two real-valued branches of the Lambert W function, W_0 (solid line) and W_{-1} (dashed line). The two branches have as their only point of agreement $x = -1/e$, where both assume the value -1 . In the remaining overlap, that is for $-1/e < x < 0$, the Lambert W function is multi-valued and the two real-valued branches assume different values for the same value of x . The W_{-1} branch has a vertical asymptote in $x = 0$, which it approaches from the left. The W_0 branch is defined for $-1/e \leq x < \infty$ and monotonically increasing in its entire domain of definition. It is also differentiable everywhere, except in the degenerate point $x = -1/e$, where it has a vertical slope.

The Lambert W function has an infinite number of branches, most of them complex-valued (in the sense of having a non-zero imaginary part). Only two branches, W_{-1} and W_0 are real-valued.

The W_{-1} branch is defined on the interval $-1/e < x < 0$ and takes values $-1 \leq W_{-1}(x) < 0$. The W_0 branch, often called the *principal branch*, is defined on the interval $-1/e < x < \infty$ and assumes values $-1 \leq W_0(x) < \infty$. The Lambert W function is thereby uniquely defined and invertible for values $0 \leq x < \infty$, where the W_0 branch provides the only (real-valued) solution. The two real-valued branches, for x between -2 and 10 , are shown in Fig. 11.

For values of x in the interval $-1/e < x < 0$, the Lambert W function is still real-valued but has multiple branches, and is therefore multi-valued (except in the unique point $x = -1/e$ where both $W_0(-1/e) = W_{-1}(-1/e) = -1$). For real parameters below $x = -1/e$, the Lambert W function is both multi-valued and all of its branches have only non-real values.

C.2 Restriction to real numbers and inversion relationship

Strictly speaking, even for the domain $x \geq 0$ the Lambert W function has an infinite number of complex-valued branches. However, the restriction of both the domain and the co-domain of $W_k(z)$, i.e. the Lambert W function on its general form, to the set of real numbers larger than or equal to zero allows for the definition

of a bijection between $W_0(x)$ and a unique inverse whose values are also non-negative. This in turn, by the definition of the Lambert W function,

$$W(z) = we^w \quad (\text{C.1})$$

now allows the definition of a restricted inversion relationship

$$W_0(x) = ue^u \quad (\text{C.2})$$

where both $x \geq 0$ and $ue^u \geq 0$.

For these reasons, it is highly advantageous if the argument of the Lambert W function can be determined to assume only real values which are equal to or larger than zero. In particular, it will be shown that this is the case for the Lambert W approximations of the Fermi-Dirac integrals which are derived in the text, and can be sharpened to strict inequality (by the fact that the argument of the Lambert W function in general is Az^B , with $A, B > 0$ and the fugacity $z = \exp(\mu/k_B T) > 0$).

C.3 Asymptotics

The principal branch $W_0(x)$ is a monotonically increasing function in x , defined on the interval $-1/e < x < \infty$. Its Maclaurin expansion is given by [6, p. 339]

$$W_0(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-k)^{k-1}}{k!} x^k. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

The expansion of $W_0(x)/x$ is therefore

$$\frac{W_0(x)}{x} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-k)^{k-1}}{k!} x^{k-1} = 1 - x + \frac{3x^2}{2} - \frac{8x^3}{3} + \mathcal{O}(x^4), \quad (\text{C.4})$$

so that for small values of x , $W_0(x) \approx x$.

Conversely, for large x , an asymptotic series is given by [6, 349]

$$W_0(x) \sim \ln x - \ln \ln x + \frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x} + \dots \quad (\text{C.5})$$

D Large- z approximation for $f_{3/2}(z)$

This section will derive an expression for the Fermi-Dirac polylogarithm $f_{3/2}(z)$ valid for large z , using the Sommerfeld expansion for low temperatures T . An existing derivation, found in Landau-Lifshitz, will be used, but this requires the integral form expression for the polylogarithm

$$f_{3/2}(z) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -\text{Li}_{3/2}(-z) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{3/2-1}}{z^{-1}e^t + 1} dt \quad (\text{D.1})$$

to be modified: $\tau \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} Tk_B$ is defined as a renormalized temperature⁵ with the dimension of energy, to conform with conventions of the cited book. This is followed by the substitutions $w = \mu/\tau$, $z = e^w$, here referring to fugacity as normal, $t = \varepsilon/\tau$, $dt = d\varepsilon/\tau$ and finally $t^{1/2} = \varepsilon^{1/2}/\tau^{1/2}$, yielding the new form

$$f_{3/2}(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)\tau^{3/2}} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon^{1/2}}{e^{(\varepsilon-\mu)/\tau} + 1} d\varepsilon. \quad (\text{D.2})$$

This is to match the form of the integral [8, p. 159, § 58]

$$I = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{f(\varepsilon)d\varepsilon}{e^{(\varepsilon-\mu)/\tau} + 1}, \quad (\text{D.3})$$

which in the book is later asymptotically expanded. (This integral is identical to its appearance in the book, except for the replacement of T by τ here.) Replacing $f(\varepsilon)$ ⁶ with

⁵ τ will here have the role as T in Landau-Lifshitz.

⁶In Landau-Lifshitz, this stands for $f(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon^{3/2}$, reflecting that the energy ε is being integrated over.

$$H(\varepsilon) = \frac{\varepsilon^{1/2}}{\Gamma(3/2)\tau^{3/2}}, \quad (\text{D.4})$$

and performing the substitution $\varepsilon - \mu = \tau\zeta$ yields

$$I = \int_{-\mu/\tau}^{\infty} \frac{H(\mu + \tau\zeta)}{e^\zeta + 1} \tau d\zeta. \quad (\text{D.5})$$

Following the derivation as in Landau-Lifshitz but with the above substitutions and notation, this reproduces the expression in Eq. (58.1) [8, 160, § 58] as

$$I = \int_0^\mu H(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon + \frac{\pi^2}{6} \tau^2 H'(\mu) + \frac{7\pi^4}{360} \tau^4 H^{(3)}(\mu) + \dots, \quad (\text{D.6})$$

this being an asymptotic expansion which fails to converge when an arbitrary number of terms is included [8, 160, § 58, footnote 1]. The first integral is simply

$$\int_0^\mu H(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon = \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)\tau^{3/2}} \left[\frac{2}{3} \varepsilon^{3/2} \right]_0^\mu = \frac{1}{(3/2)\Gamma(3/2)\tau^{3/2}} \mu^{3/2} = \frac{\mu^{3/2}}{\Gamma(5/2)\tau^{3/2}}. \quad (\text{D.7})$$

The following terms (powers of two and four in τ) are calculated by taking the first and third derivatives of $H(\mu)$ respectively:

$$H'(\mu) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)\tau^{3/2}} \frac{1}{2} \mu^{-1/2} \quad (\text{D.8})$$

and

$$H^{(3)}(\mu) = \frac{3}{8} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)\tau^{3/2}} \mu^{-5/2}. \quad (\text{D.9})$$

Recalling that $w \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mu/\tau$, which gives $\mu = w\tau$, and combining prefactors and powers of τ in each term, this gives for the first term

$$\frac{\mu^{3/2}}{\Gamma(5/2)\tau^{3/2}} = \frac{w^{3/2}}{\Gamma(5/2)}, \quad (\text{D.10})$$

for the second term

$$\frac{\pi^2}{12} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\tau^2}{\tau^{3/2}} \mu^{-1/2} = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} \tau^{1/2} \mu^{-1/2} = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} w^{-1/2}, \quad (\text{D.11})$$

and finally for the third term

$$\frac{7\pi^4}{360} \frac{3}{8} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)\tau^{3/2}} \tau^4 \mu^{-5/2} = \frac{7\pi^4}{960} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} \tau^{5/2} \mu^{-5/2} = \frac{7\pi^4}{960} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} w^{-5/2}. \quad (\text{D.12})$$

With $\Gamma(5/2)/\Gamma(3/2) = 3/2$ and $\Gamma(5/2) = 3\sqrt{\pi}/4$, this finally yields the asymptotic expansion

$$\begin{aligned} f_{3/2}(z) &= f_{3/2}(e^w) = \frac{w^{3/2}}{\Gamma(5/2)} + \frac{\pi^2}{12} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} w^{-1/2} + \frac{7\pi^4}{960} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3/2)} w^{-5/2} + \dots \\ &= \frac{w^{3/2}}{\Gamma(5/2)} \left[1 + \frac{2}{3} \frac{\pi^2}{12} w^{-2} + \frac{2}{3} \frac{7\pi^4}{960} w^{-4} + \dots \right] \\ &= \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} w^{3/2} \left[1 + \frac{\pi^2}{8} w^{-2} + \frac{7\pi^4}{640} w^{-4} \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.13})$$

At this point, the standard absolute temperature T can be reintroduced, with $w = \mu/\tau = \mu/k_B T$ and $z = e^w = \exp(\mu/k_B T)$.

Note that, given $w = \ln z$, the expansion can also be expressed in terms of $\ln z$ as

$$f_{3/2}(\ln z) = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} (\ln z)^{3/2} \left[1 + \frac{\pi^2}{8} (\ln z)^{-2} + \frac{7\pi^4}{640} (\ln z)^{-4} \dots \right]. \quad (\text{D.14})$$

Acknowledgements

I thank the library of the Chalmers University of Technology and its wonderful staff for lending out to me what must be a significant share of their books on statistical mechanics and asymptotic analysis.

I also thank CERN and the Zenodo team for demonstrating how scientific publishing can be free of institutional barriers; open to everyone who believes, rightly or wrongly, that they have something to contribute.

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